

Screen Printed Electrochemical Sensors: Textile Effect on pH Sensing

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Abstract— This research examines the influence of textile-based, screen-printed carbon electrodes on pH sensing. The electrochemical sensors are printed on knitted and woven textile substrates. Optical profilometry is used to explore the textile and printed electrodes' structures. The knitted and woven polyester/cotton textile-based electrochemical sensors are tested for redox probes and pH. For screen printed electrodes on both textiles, the cyclic voltammograms are recorded from -1 to 1V with a scan rate of 0.05 V s^{-1} . The anodic and cathodic peaks are observed for redox probing and pH solutions. The sensitivity of knitted textiles is 0.019 V/pH , and that of woven textiles is 0.011 V/pH . The maximum peak current of $27.73 \mu\text{A}$ is recorded for pH4 on knitted textiles. The decrease in peak current and peak potential is observed with an increase in pH scale for both textiles. The analysis of experimental results shows that knitted textiles of different structures and materials can be explored in the future for sensing different analytes like glucose and lactate in sweat.

Keywords— carbon electrodes, fabric, pH, screen printed electrodes, textile structure

I. INTRODUCTION

For the health monitoring application, flexible chemical sensors can be useful to provide data about the wearer's health [1]. Textiles represent an attractive class of substrates for fabricating such wearable chemical sensors. Textiles are considered suitable substrates for the fabrication of wearable chemical sensors due to their unique properties. These properties can be tailored for numerous applications where comfortability and durability are critical criteria [2].

The human skin provides information about human health by monitoring the pH. Different kinds of skin diseases, for example, any fungal infection or dermatitis, are the result of a change in skin pH [3]. The dehydration state of the human body due to heatstroke or strenuous exercise can also be checked through the change in skin pH. The range for healthy skin is 4.2-5.6; in cases of dehydration, the pH shifts to basic value [4]. To improve the comfortability and compatibility of flexible pH sensors, the potential strategy is to use textile substrates rather than film substrates. Textile substrates for measuring skin pH are generally nontoxic and deformable without affecting intrinsic, physical, or chemical properties [5].

For example, researchers fabricated textile-based sensors to measure sweat pH [6]. The stainless-steel conductive fabric electrodeposited with an iridium oxide film showed high Different types of conductive fabric, such as a stainless-steel mesh with an electrodeposited iridium oxide film, displayed good sensitivity to the pH change from 4 to 8. Although it has great sensitivity, but

the sensor made of rigid inorganic materials may limit flexibility and resistance to repetitive deformation. Hence, in fiber-based sensors, there is always a trade-off between yarn softness and hardness. Despite substantial advancements in sensor durability, they remain constrained to simple electrode designs and substrates, neither of which is commercially available [7]. The screen-printing technique is fast, inexpensive, and good for the mass production of microelectrodes. The sensors fabricated by this technique show robustness and the ability to print different shapes of sensors. Electrochemical sensors have made substantial progress with the development of a wide range of functional pastes for screen-printing technology. Furthermore, because the printing process for clothing already exists, there is no need for significant investment or R&D costs to incorporate it into clothing for mass production of garments [7], [8]. This makes the technology very accessible and appealing for industrial use. Although the screen-printing process is scalable and attractive for developing wearable electrochemical sensors, However, the compatibility of various textile materials with the thick-film sensor manufacturing method is not explored much. The present research examines the impact of different textiles on the performance of screen-printed electrodes (SPE) for pH sensing. In particular, differences in the weaving or knitting pattern of the textile substrate are shown to have a profound effect on the sensing behavior of SPE.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

A. Materials

Potassium ferricyanide $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$, potassium ferrocyanide $[K_4Fe(CN)_6]$, and potassium chloride (KCl) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. The commercially available solutions with pH values of 4, 5, 7, 8, and 12 were purchased from Alfapanon. Textile substrates were bought from local market. Carbon conductive paste DuPont 7102 (DuPont de Nemours, Inc., USA) was used for screen-printing on textiles. For sensor fabrication, an Aurel automation VS1520 screen-printing machine (Aurel Automation, Italy) was used. Following the screen-printing of the patterns onto textile, the printed structures were put in the sintering oven (Memert GmbH, Germany) at $85^\circ C$ for 30 minutes to cure the conductive pastes.

B. Characterization of Sensor

5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ in 0.1 M of KCl was prepared using deionized (DI) water. The PalmSens4 instrument was used to perform electrochemical measurements. The Bluetooth connection was established between the PalmSens4 and laptop. The working electrode, counter electrode, and reference electrode were carbon, carbon, and the Ag/AgCl, respectively. The 6 μL volume of the redox solution and pH solution was used in the electrochemical measurements. Cyclic voltammetry analysis was performed in the potential window from -1 to 1 V (vs. Ag/AgCl reference electrode). The potential scan rate was 0.05 V s^{-1} .

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Sensor fabrication and testing

Fig. 1(a,b) shows the textile-based printed electrodes on two different textiles Fig. 1(c,d) represents the experimental setup for the sensor testing.

Fig. 1. Screen printed sensors and experimental setup: (a) tex 1 (b) tex 2 (c) experimental setup to test the sensors.

B. Surface characterization of textile and printed electrodes

Fig. 2 represents the optical images of two different kinds of textiles with screen printed electrodes. Fig. 2 (a, c) shows the images of bare textiles named tex1 and tex 2. Both textiles have dense structures and are blends of cotton and polyester, but tex1 is knitted fabric and tex2 is woven fabric. Fig. 2(b, d) displays the images of printed electrodes on tex1 and tex2, respectively.

Fig. 2. Optical profilometry images (a) tex 1 (b) printed working electrode on tex 1 (c) tex 2 (d) printed working electrode on tex 2.

The rough surface of the printed electrodes is visible in the images. In the next section, we will discuss the impact of textiles on pH sensing due to their different structures.

C. Electrochemical measurement

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) is an analytical method used to characterize and investigate the electrochemical behavior of different textiles for pH sensing. The electrochemical behavior is presented as a Cyclic Voltammogram (CV) by plotting the potential range as a function of the corresponding current density. Fig. 3 represents the shape of the CV curve observed for carbon-based screen-printed electrodes on two different textiles for 5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ in 0.1 M of KCl. Fig. 3(a) shows the anodic current (i_{pa}) and potential (E_{pa}) for tex 1 electrode.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of SPCE recorded for 5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ in 0.1M of KCl (a) tex 1 (b) tex 2.

The recorded value is $18.84\mu\text{A}$ and 0.129 V for i_{pa} and E_{pa} respectively whereas cathodic current (i_{pc}) and (E_{pc}) value is $-17.30\mu\text{A}$ and -0.2 V , respectively. Fig. 3(b) represents the CV for tex 2 electrode. For tex 2 i_{pa} , E_{pa} , i_{pc} and E_{pc} values are $4.233\mu\text{A}$, 0.149 V , $-1.367\mu\text{A}$ and -0.370 V .

The tex 1 represents the typical curve of $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]/\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$. Both textiles have shown the oxidation and reduction peaks but for the tex 1 the peaks are broad and current is high as compared to the tex 2 which has shown the sharp increase in current at oxidation and reduction peak. Another point is observed in the difference in anodic and cathodic current. The ratio I_a/I_p for tex 1 is 1.08 whereas for tex 2 the ratio is 0.10 which explains the quasi reversible-reversible for tex 1 and quasi reversible-irreversible for tex 2 [9] [10]. The difference in the shape of CV curves depends on electrodes material, scan rate, concentration of electrolyte, temperature and surface properties of electrode [11]. In the present research, all other parameters were constant except surface properties of textile-based screen-printed electrodes. The porosity, surface roughness and active sites on the surface of electrodes play the key role in redox reaction [12]. The rough surface means microstructure or irregularities on the surface of electrode as can be seen in Fig. 2 (b,d). Both textiles have rough surface but tex 1 microstructure is different than tex 2. We can see microstructural irregularities on the surface of tex 1 printed electrodes. Whereas tex 2 has porous structure. Surface roughness leads to the higher active sites which facilitate the redox reaction by showing the broader peaks but porosity controls the reaction kinetic through the diffusion and mass transport. Lower the surface porosity slower the diffusion process which appears as the broad peak.

Fig. 4 illustrates the CVs recorded at varying pH (pH4, pH5, pH7, pH8, pH12). Fig. 4(a) shows the results of carbon-based printed electrodes on tex 1. The anodic and cathodic peaks are prominent for acidic pH (4,5) and peak shift was observed towards negative potential whereas for neutral pH (7) and basic pH (8,12). The anodic and cathodic peak currents are higher at lower pH.

The relationship between pH and electrode potential is also obvious through the shift in potentials of the peaks with varying pH. Fig. 4(b) represents the pH response of the electrode printed on tex 2. For varied pH values, the anodic current increases fast from -0.1 V to 0.2 V , then levels off, and a gradual increase is observed up to 1 V . However, the change in current magnitude in both CV curves indicate the sensitivity to pH [13]. The variation in peak separation is also observed as the pH value shift towards the higher scale due to non homogeneous surface of printed electrode.

Fig. 4. CV curve of varying pH solutions on printed electrodes (a) tex 1 (b) tex 2.

Fig. 5(a) represents the variation in peak current (I_p), and Fig. 5(b) shows the change in potential (E_p) with a change in pH.

The higher value of peak current for tex 1 indicates that the the higher mass transfer during the redox reaction and the potential of the electrode with changing pH are influenced by the active sites on the electrode surface. The higher value of E_p indicates the presence of active sites on tex 2 [14].

The sensitivity for the both textiles is also calculated from the E_p vs pH graph using equation 1.

$$\frac{\Delta E_p}{\Delta pH} \quad (1)$$

The sensitivity is 0.02 V/pH for tex1 and 0.01 V/pH for tex 2. The knitted textile tex 1 shows the impact of electrode microstructure and roughness on sensitivity and peak current with a change in pH.

Fig. 5. Change in peak potential with pH for tex 1 and tex 2.

Knitted textiles (tex 1) are more sensitive to pH solutions than woven textiles because of their fundamental structure and composition. Knitted fabrics have a porous structure due to interlooping yarns. The wide spaces provide better interaction with pH solutions. Woven fabrics, made by interlacing two sets of threads, have a denser and more robust structure. Their closely woven structure limits pH solution penetration [15].

CONCLUSION

We have printed the carbon-based electrodes on two different textile structures and tested them for the redox probe through cyclic voltametry. The redox probe gave both anodic and cathodic peaks for tex 1 and tex 2. The broader peak for tex 1 has shown the gradual process of oxidation and reduction, whereas the sharp increase in the CV curve of tex 2 proved the oxidation on the electrode surface. The electrodes influence was also examined for pH sensing. The sensitivity peak current

and peak separation for pH (4,5,7) are higher for tex 1. Hence, the knitted structure of tex 1 has revealed its prominent impact on pH sensing. The sensitivity of the pH sensor can be further improved by testing different structures of knitted textiles. Also, the knitted structures can be explored for glucose and lactate sensing in sweat.

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